
Evolution of Prakrit and Contribution to Indian Knowledge System

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Abstract Indian ancient traditional knowledge system is a unique and has many roots of learning relevant to anytime. It has involved, and different chapters of ancient Indian knowledge are classified into various sections. Therefore, there is a need to analyse the nature and history of that knowledge. Research empathizes the importance of regional languages. Linguistic diversity and cultural heritage in education recognising their role in promoting a deeper understanding of India's knowledge system. The IKS surrounds a vast body of knowledge developed over millennia and Prakrit languages played a crucial role in its transmission and preservation. Research highlights the importance of regional languages in presenting and Disseminating IKS. Prakrit, as a vernacular language of ancient India served as the medium for disseminating teaching and philosophical ideas contributing significantly to the understanding of Indian history culture and literation. Prakrit influence can be seen in the development of later languages like Hindi, and it provides valuable insights into the evolution of Indian languages.

Keywords: Enduring, Meticulously, Evolving, Emphasizing, vernacular.

Introduction

It is proudly known that our prime minister Mr. Narendra Modi ji declared Prakrit as a 'SHASTRI' language or classical language on 3rd October 2024. Prakrit is a middle-Indo-Aryan language and helpful to understanding India's rich linguistic and cultural heritage. It is not only an ancient language but gives the foundation to many modern Indian languages. Like Sanskrit it is also a real vehicle of Indian wisdom.

History

when will look at the Indian literacy tradition, we find that writers of other languages have compare their work based on Prakrit literature. To gain complete knowledge of Indian civilization culture and literature it is necessary to study Prakrit language. Prakrit is a oldest common language of the world's largest democracy India. It has been a simple and natural medium of expression of folk life since ancient times. There has been an exchange of emotions, thoughts and knowledge between Prakrit and Sanskrit full stop when we talk about the story tradition of Prakrit, then Brihatkhatha of Mahakavi Gunadhy is considered to be the original source of Indian story literature.

Importance

Literature is the mirror of society. Literature presents a true picture of the events that happened in society and is not limited to any language, country society or individual but is universal and national. Similarity is found in the literature of all the languages of the world.

Prakrit language: It is one of the oldest languages in the world. Apbransh has developed from Prakrit and regional languages have developed from a Apbransh. Prakrit language and literature have an important contribution in the study of Indian literature and the languages used in it. Important literatures of Indian literature are available in Prakrit language. Proof of which are the world's oldest stone inscription records and manuscripts.

Development of Prakrit:-

Indo - European, Semitic, Hamitic, monosyllabic, Ural, Dravidian, Malo -Paleolithic, Batu African, Australian, American etc. are language families. Prakrit belongs to the European family. It was earlier called 'Arsham' which was considered to the language of sages and saints.

The Aryabhata family is divided into three ages:-

(i) The entire alphabet is written in Anyabhasas.

1. Old Indo - Aryan Period

2. Middle Aryan Kaal

3. Modern Aryabhasha period

It was common language in Vedic age also. The Sanskrit form of disciplined and refined language was declared as Sanskrit.

Ahardev Bahri said that ancient and medieval Aryan language developed from the common language Prakrit language gets continuous expansion along with knowledge and civilization.

Their literary forms also spread through Prakrit. The naturally derived language. Prakrit gained a valuable place due to the revolutionary elements.

What comes from nature is natural. Nature means, the easy trade of all living beings. Prakrit considered as the language of the people and stated that all languages developed from this language.

Contribution of Prakrit in the development of Indian languages:-

The language born from nature is Prakrit . It is a language of the common people. Since ancient times. This Prakrit language changed a little according to different provinces and countries and become famous by the names of Magadhi , Shauraseni, Maharastri , Avanti Etc. Prakrit

language got different names according to different Countries. There was some difference in its forms and pronunciation also. It is also called Mother of modern Aryan language Family. Over time, the form of that Prakrit language changed into many different forms according places. We can say that Prakrit language has not originated from any other language, but all languages have originated from this Prakrit only In the early centuries of Christ. Prakrit language started spreading from the huts of villages to the places and royal courts and it was chosen as a powerful medium of expression When the folk language becomes popular among the people and when its vocabulary increases, then it also starts becoming the language of poetry. Prakrit language has this good fortune in two ways. Firstly, it has a huge collection of Agamas and their interpretation literature and secondly a large number of stories, poems and biographies etc. have been written in it. which contain poetic beauty.

The melody of the Prakrit language:-

There was a time when the Prakrit language had such a golden age that it had the highest place in the expression of sweet and sweeter subjects. This is the reason that the best poets of that time made Prakrit the main medium for the creation of their epics.

Why should those who neither know how to read nor listen to the elixir of 'Prakrit Poetry' feel ashamed to discuss the essence of the work?

The need for language skills in modern times:-

In the present time the practice of Indian languages has become mandatory. People from other countries came to India and were attracted to Indian culture and started studying Indian languages. Today Indian languages are being practiced across the world. In the modern era, people despite being physically isolated, are coming in contact with each other through the internet and mobile. In this situation, knowledge of more than one language has also become mandatory. Western scholars have written books on Indian languages after studying them. Sanskrit is considered to be the ancient language of India, but the contemporary Prakrit language has changed at different times and is now available in the form of various regional languages. Today the languages spoken in India are

more related to Prakrit than Sanskrit. It is important to study the literature of Prakrit language for the revision of Indian languages.

Measures for the development and presentation of Prakrit language.

The Prakrit language has a special place among Indian languages. The facts of Indian life values are contained in the Prakrit language. This was a common language in ancient times, that is why Jain Acharyas mostly used the Prakrit language as the medium of their writings. Over time, this language did not get state patronage. As a result, its influence and propagation decreased. Prakrit language has become invisible in Indian literature. Many people do not even know that 'Prakrit' is also a language. So it is the ultimate duty of the followers and lovers of the Indian language to make efforts for the development and presentation of the oriental language Prakrit.

The following efforts should be made:-

- **Public awareness** - We should make public awareness for the Prakrit language because only through we can know the values of life written in 'Shruti'.
- **Encourage people to study Prakrit** - Many universities run many graduations and post-graduation, certificate courses, diploma etc. The number. of students everywhere is minimal. So, from time-to-time information articles in all newspapers and magazines should be published.
- **To give special motivation** - There should be a system of studying Prakrit through correspondence courses.
- **Establishment of scholarship funds for Prakrit** - To encourage these adequate funds should be established so that Prakrit-lovers can be encouraged by providing them scholarships.
- **Establishment of a research institute** - A research institute should have high-level research of Prakrit manuscripts. A plan should be made for English translation of Prakrit texts.
- **Establishment of Prakrit Academy** - The new education policy has been established for the Prakrit academy. We should make continuous efforts by repeatedly submitting your requests to the state government.
- **Organize Education camps** - In vacations regular education camps should be organized for Gen. knowledge of Prakrit language. Every person can gain knowledge of Prakrit by these camps.
- **Study of Prakrit is mandatory**
- **Employment through Prakrit**

Summary

According to all the aspects of Prakrit we can easily say that Prakrit should not be seen or related to any religion, cast or literature. Apart from these it is related to Indian moral values, cultural, and life. It should have the attention of intelligent people and take part in the growth of Prakrit.

We should worry about the future of Prakrit in our country so that our future generation can become well versed in the moral values, its history, traditions and become self-confident because if we lose the ability to read the entirety of these ancient valuable languages and knowledge then we will lose the essential and basic things for human life.

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